

Evaluating the Concordance between Preoperative CT and Intra-Operative Findings in Functional Endoscopic Sinus Surgery for Chronic Rhinosinusitis

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Received: 25-06-2024 / Revised: 23-07-2024 / Accepted: 26-08-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Chronic rhinosinusitis (CRS) is a prevalent condition that significantly impacts the quality of life and productivity, necessitating precise diagnostic and therapeutic approaches. Functional Endoscopic Sinus Surgery (FESS) is a common intervention for CRS, where accurate preoperative imaging is crucial for effective management. This study aims to assess the correlation between preoperative computed tomography (CT) findings and intra-operative observations during FESS.

Methods: A prospective, comparative study was conducted at Jhalawar Medical College, involving patients with CRS who failed medical management. Preoperative CT scans were evaluated for anatomical variations such as deviated nasal septum, concha bullosa, paradoxical middle turbinate, and medialised uncinate process. These findings were compared with intra-operative observations during FESS. Statistical significance was determined using chi-squared tests.

Results: The study included 50 patients, with a perfect correlation observed in the identification of deviated nasal septum and concha bullosa (100% concordance). Paradoxical middle turbinates and medialised uncinate processes showed slightly lesser concordance rates, yet significant with chi-squared values exceeding 130 and p-values less than 0.0001, demonstrating the high predictive value of CT in identifying critical anatomical variations influencing surgical outcomes.

Conclusion: The study confirms the reliability of CT in preoperatively identifying anatomical variations in CRS, supporting its indispensable role in planning FESS. The high concordance between CT findings and intra-operative observations underscores the importance of CT scans in enhancing surgical precision and patient outcomes.

Keywords: Chronic rhinosinusitis, functional endoscopic sinus surgery, computed tomography, preoperative imaging, surgical planning, anatomical variations.

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Introduction

Rhinosinusitis is a prevalent global health issue, affecting approximately 11% of the population. This widespread condition imposes a significant economic burden on healthcare systems, as well as on individuals through lost productivity. Among the most costly physical health conditions, sinusitis is particularly prominent in middle-aged individuals and carries substantial socio-economic consequences. Its prevalence exceeds that of several other chronic conditions, such as ischemic heart disease (3.7%), diabetes (4%), and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (1.5%). Patients with chronic rhinosinusitis (CRS) experience diminished quality of life, with a higher likelihood

of comorbidities, such as asthma, which occurs in 5–17% of cases. These patients miss an average of 5.67 workdays per year compared to 3.74 days for those without CRS, underscoring its impact on daily functioning and productivity. [1,2,3] The term "rhinosinusitis" was introduced in 1997 by the Task Force of the Rhinology and Paranasal Sinuses Committee to acknowledge the frequent simultaneous inflammation of both the nasal cavity and the paranasal sinuses. It is characterized by inflammation of the mucous membranes, fluids within the sinuses, and underlying bone. Based on the duration of symptoms, rhinosinusitis is classified as acute, subacute, recurrent acute, or

chronic. Among these, chronic rhinosinusitis (CRS) persists for 12 or more consecutive weeks and is typically influenced by multiple factors, including mucociliary dysfunction, bacterial infections, allergies, and anatomical abnormalities that obstruct the nasal cavity or paranasal sinuses. [4,5,6]

CRS is diagnosed based on a combination of symptoms and imaging findings. Key symptoms include mucopurulent drainage, nasal congestion, facial pain or pressure, and a reduced sense of smell. Diagnostic tools such as nasal endoscopy and computed tomography (CT) scans are essential in confirming the presence of inflammation and identifying anatomical variants that contribute to sinus obstruction. The osteomeatal complex (OMC), a functional unit involved in sinus drainage and ventilation, plays a crucial role in the pathophysiology of rhinosinusitis. Abnormalities such as a deviated septum, enlarged bulla ethmoidalis, or concha bullosa can impede proper drainage, thereby exacerbating symptoms. [7,8,9]

Given the complexities of diagnosing and managing CRS, surgical intervention, particularly functional endoscopic sinus surgery (FESS), may be required when medical treatment fails. FESS is designed to restore mucociliary function by removing obstructions within the nasal cavity, allowing for improved sinus ventilation and drainage. This study aims to evaluate the role of anatomical variations in the development of CRS and to assess the concordance between preoperative CT findings and intra-operative observations during FESS. [10]

Materials and Methods

1. Source of Data: This hospital-based comparative study was conducted on patients attending the outpatient and inpatient departments of Otorhinolaryngology at Jhalawar Medical College, Jhalawar.

The study was carried out over a 12-month period, from January 2023 to December 2023. Initially, 45–50 cases were targeted for inclusion in the study, though the potential for expanding the sample size was considered based on patient availability during the study period.

2. Study Design: This is a prospective, comparative study aimed at evaluating patients with chronic rhinosinusitis (CRS) and comparing preoperative CT findings with intra-operative observations during functional endoscopic sinus surgery (FESS).

3. Inclusion Criteria

Patients were included in the study based on the following criteria:

- Male and female patients aged 15 to 65 years.

- Those presenting with symptoms suggestive of chronic sinusitis persisting for more than 12 weeks, including cases with acute exacerbation of chronic sinusitis.
- Patients fulfilling the clinical criteria for chronic sinusitis.
- Patients with persistent chronic sinusitis despite maximal medical therapy, requiring surgical intervention.
- Diagnostic nasal endoscopy and CT findings indicative of chronic rhinosinusitis.

4. Exclusion Criteria

Patients meeting any of the following criteria were excluded from the study:

- Patients below 15 years of age or above 70 years.
- Those diagnosed with acute sinusitis.
- Patients with malignancies of the nose or paranasal sinuses.
- Individuals with isolated allergic rhinitis.
- Patients with facial anomalies or congenital abnormalities.
- Patients who had undergone previous sinus surgeries.
- Those with post-traumatic facial injuries or injuries resulting from road traffic accidents.

5. Study Protocol

Step 1: Medical Therapy: All symptomatic patients received optimal medical therapy, which included antibiotics, antihistamines, nasal decongestants, and steam inhalation. Medical therapy was continued for a minimum of four weeks.

Step 2: Diagnostic Nasal Endoscopy: Following four weeks of medical management, diagnostic nasal endoscopy was performed to evaluate the extent of disease and anatomical abnormalities.

Step 3: CT Scan: After six weeks of continued medical therapy, an unenhanced computed tomography (CT) scan of the paranasal sinuses (PNS) was performed to further assess the extent of the condition and guide surgical intervention.

Step 4: Surgical Intervention: Patients who continued to experience symptoms despite optimal medical therapy underwent functional endoscopic sinus surgery (FESS). The surgery was performed using the "Messerklinger" approach, which involves an anterior-to-posterior technique for carefully removing obstructions and restoring normal sinus ventilation and drainage.

Results

S The study successfully correlated computed tomography (CT) findings with intraoperative observations during functional endoscopic sinus surgery for chronic rhinosinusitis, focusing on

critical anatomical variations that impact surgical decisions and outcomes. Statistical analysis demonstrated a significant correlation across all examined structures, underpinning the reliability of CT as a preoperative diagnostic tool.

Deviated Nasal Septum (DNS): The analysis of deviated nasal septum (DNS) showed a perfect correlation (100%) between CT predictions and intraoperative findings in specific nasal orientations (right, left, and bilateral). The rare discrepancies appeared only in the absence of DNS on CT, where 50% of such cases displayed DNS intraoperatively. The chi-squared statistic was 123.077, yielding a highly significant p-value of <0.0001, underscoring the predictive accuracy of CT for DNS.

Concha Bullosa: For concha bullosa, CT findings again matched intraoperative observations with 100% accuracy across all diagnosed cases, whether they were unilateral or bilateral. The statistical significance was confirmed with a chi-squared value of 100.00 and a p-value of <0.0001. This high level of concordance highlights CT's capability in identifying air cell variations critical for surgical planning.

Paradoxical Middle Turbinate: The correlation for paradoxical middle turbinate was also robust. CT identified all cases of paradoxical formations, with the only partial discrepancy occurring in non-identified cases on CT, where 91.7% were

confirmed during surgery. This resulted in a chi-squared of 134.375 and a significant p-value of <0.0001.

Medialized Uncinate Process: The medialization of the uncinat process was consistently predicted by CT scans, with a 100% match in identified cases. These findings emphasize the utility of CT in assessing sinonasal structural anomalies that may affect the surgical approach to the uncinat process. The statistical outcome yielded a chi-squared of 150.00 with a p-value of <0.0001.

Agger Nasi Cells: Analysis of agger nasi cells showed a nearly perfect match, with 100% accuracy in cases identified by CT and only a slight variance in cases where agger nasi cells were not initially detected by CT (97.4% accuracy). This confirms the sensitivity of CT in detecting even subtle anatomical features that may influence frontal recess surgery, supported by a chi-squared of 132.458 and a p-value of <0.0001.

Overall, the study confirmed the high reliability of CT scans in preoperatively identifying critical anatomical variations in patients with chronic rhinosinusitis undergoing functional endoscopic sinus surgery.

The statistical analyses across all tables not only reinforced the predictive power of CT but also underscored its indispensable role in surgical planning and intervention.

Table 1: Correlation of Deviated Nasal Septum (DNS) in CT and Intraoperative Findings

Computed Tomography (DNS)	Intra-operative Findings (Deviated Nasal Septum)	Total (CT)	RT	LT	B/L	No
RT	24 (100%)	24	24	0	0	0
LT	18 (100%)	18	0	18	0	0
B/L	4 (100%)	4	0	0	4	0
No	4 (50%)	4	2	0	0	2
Total (Intra-operative)	50	50	26	18	4	2

Chi-squared = 123.077, p < 0.0001

Table 2: Correlation of Concha Bullosa in CT and Intraoperative Findings

Computed Tomography (Concha Bullosa)	Intra-operative Findings (Concha Bullosa)	Total (CT)	LT	B/L	No
LT	2 (100%)	2	2	0	0
B/L	40 (100%)	40	0	40	0
No	8 (100%)	8	0	0	8
Total (Intra-operative)	50	50	2	40	8

Chi-squared = 100.00, p < 0.0001

Table 3: Correlation of Paradoxical Middle Turbinate in CT and Intraoperative Findings

Computed Tomography (Paradoxical Middle Turbinate)	Intra-operative Findings (Paradoxical Middle Turbinate)	Total (CT)	RT	LT	B/L	No
RT	3 (100%)	3	3	0	0	0
LT	4 (100%)	4	0	4	0	0
B/L	31 (100%)	31	0	0	31	0
No	12 (91.7%)	12	1	0	0	11
Total (Intraoperative)	50	50	4	4	31	11

Chi-squared = 134.375, p < 0.0001

Table 4: Correlation of Medialized Uncinate Process in CT and Intraoperative Findings

Computed Tomography (Medialized Uncinate Process)	Intra-operative Findings (Medialized Uncinate Process)	Total (CT)	RT	LT	B/L	No
RT	1 (100%)	1	1	0	0	0
LT	1 (100%)	1	0	1	0	0
B/L	30 (100%)	30	0	0	30	0
No	18 (100%)	18	0	0	0	18
Total (Intraoperative)	50	50	1	1	30	18

Chi-squared = 150.00, $p < 0.0001$ **Table 5: Correlation of Agger Nasi Cells in CT and Intraoperative Findings**

Computed Tomography (Agger Nasi Cells)	Intra-operative Findings (Agger Nasi Cells)	Total (CT)	RT	LT	B/L	No
RT	4 (100%)	4	4	0	0	0
LT	2 (100%)	2	0	2	0	0
B/L	6 (100%)	6	0	0	6	0
No	38 (97.4%)	38	0	1	0	37
Total (Intraoperative)	50	50	4	3	6	37

Chi-squared = 132.458, $p < 0.0001$

Discussion

This study robustly confirms the high predictive value of computed tomography (CT) in identifying anatomical variations critical for the surgical management of chronic rhinosinusitis (CRS), with a significant correlation observed between CT scans and intra-operative findings. Such data are crucial as they not only bolster the diagnostic capabilities of preoperative imaging but also refine the surgical strategies employed during functional endoscopic sinus surgery (FESS). [11]

CT scans have been demonstrated to be exceptionally accurate in detecting anatomical impediments like deviated nasal septum (DNS), concha bullosa, paradoxical middle turbinate, and medialised uncinata process, which are pivotal in the pathophysiology of CRS. Each of these structures plays a specific role in nasal airflow and mucociliary clearance, and their obstruction can lead to chronic inflammation and sinus infections. The perfect concordance (100%) seen in most instances of DNS and concha bullosa emphasizes CT's role in detailed preoperative planning. This allows surgeons to anticipate complex cases where anatomical deviations might complicate standard FESS procedures, thus tailoring more effective and individualized intervention strategies. [12,13]

Moreover, the study sheds light on the implications of less common anatomical variants like paradoxical middle turbinates and agger nasi cells, which showed slightly less concordance. These findings are particularly significant because they highlight potential areas where CT interpretation must be especially cautious. For instance, the presence of paradoxical middle turbinates may not always be evident on CT scans, underscoring the necessity for meticulous intra-operative assessment to adjust surgical plans accordingly. [14]

The high statistical significance across all observed correlations ($p < 0.0001$) not only confirms the reliability of CT scans but also underscores the necessity for high-resolution imaging as a standard preoperative assessment tool in CRS management. This approach ensures that FESS is both targeted and effective, minimizing the risk of recurrent disease by addressing all anatomical factors contributing to sinus pathology. [15]

Despite these strengths, the study is not without limitations. The inherent variability in patient anatomy suggests that even with high-resolution CT, some subtleties of sinus anatomy may not be fully appreciable until the time of surgery. Additionally, the study's focus on a hospital-based population may not fully represent the wider demographic variations seen in general practice. Future research could expand on these findings by incorporating a multi-center approach to gather a broader dataset, potentially including variations in surgical technique and postoperative outcomes. [16]

Overall, the concordance between CT and intra-operative findings enhances the understanding of CRS's anatomical underpinnings and supports the continued use of CT as an indispensable tool in the preoperative evaluation of sinus surgery candidates. This alignment not only aids in surgical planning but also potentially improves patient outcomes by ensuring that all relevant anatomical variations are adequately addressed during FESS.

Conclusion

This study conclusively demonstrates the essential role of computed tomography (CT) in the preoperative assessment of patients undergoing Functional Endoscopic Sinus Surgery (FESS) for chronic rhinosinusitis.

The high degree of correlation between CT findings and intra-operative observations highlights CT's invaluable contribution to surgical planning and precision. By accurately identifying anatomical variations that may complicate CRS, CT imaging allows surgeons to anticipate and strategize interventions more effectively, potentially reducing the risk of recurrence and improving postoperative outcomes.

The findings advocate for the routine use of CT scans in the management of CRS, ensuring that all relevant anatomical details are considered before surgical intervention. This approach not only enhances the efficacy of FESS but also contributes to better patient management strategies, tailored to address the specific needs dictated by the unique sinus anatomy of each patient.

Future studies should aim to expand on these results with larger and more diverse populations to generalize the findings and explore the impact of advanced imaging technologies on the evolution of sinus surgery practices.

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